

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE HISTORY OF THE JEWISH COMMUNITY OF FAGARAS (ROMANIA)

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Abstract

The information regarding the study of the Jewish presence in Transylvania is relatively substantial, the main characteristic in the analysis of this minority is that there can be found the first reports about it, which consist in a series of documents about the 11th century Kingdom of Hungary and its problems. On the other hand, the studies and historical documents are written more thoroughly allowing a more precise analysis than their equivalents in the other areas of Romania.

In this article we are trying through real contributions, for the first time, to outline a history of the Jewish presence in the city of Fagaras (between the end of the 17th century and the beginning of the 2000s), the heart of a geographical area filled with history – Fagaras County –, located in the South-Southeast of Transylvania.

Keywords: Jews, Fagaras, history, demography, confession, school, economy.

History

Over the centuries, among the ethnic groups who found on the Romanian territory a favorable environment for their affirmation and development, were also the Jews, which represented one of the relatively numerous nationalities in this country, and the province of Transylvania knew their presence as early as from the oldest times.

For Transylvania, the documents, which deal with a series of problems of the Kingdom of Hungary, are mentioning for the first time the presence of the Jews in the 11th and 12th centuries, such as the Decree of Ladislaus I, from 1092, among whose provisions there was also the one of banning mixed marriages between Jews and Christians, as well as other punitive regulations against the existent stable Jewish communities at that time in the Kingdom, whose members most likely came from Western Europe. The reports had become more frequent in the following century, among them standing out the one through which the Hungarian king Bela IV (1235-1270) employed Jews in public positions and construction work.

Located in the South-Southeast of Transylvania, the market and then the city of Fagaras knew their stable presence relatively late, at the end of the 18th century, but the first contacts with them date two and a half centuries earlier, around the middle of the 16th century. Thus, from a letter dated 9th of May 1551 and sent from Fagaras by the wife of the former voivode of Transylvania, Ștefan Mailat (killed by the Turks in the famous prison Yedikule in Istanbul), to his brother, the Baron Tamás Nádasdy, we learn that, along with a priest, Abraham the Jew was his intermediary at the Ottoman Porte [1, 32].

According to other documents, the next contact of the Jews with Fagaras took place towards the end of the 17th century, when their delegates presented themselves in the Fortress of Fagaras – princely estate –, in front of Prince Mihály Apafi I, requesting a settlement approval for few Jewish families in the city. Their request was not accepted, but they were told that they could settle in the village of Porumbacu de Sus, near the glass fac-

tory from there, founded a few decades earlier by another prince, Bethlen Gábor. In 1697, two Sephardi Jews (arriving from Spain), Abraham B. Avigdor and Abraham B. Naftalin, leased the factory from Porumbacu de Sus for the manufacture of glass products, being followed by other Jews who settled there. Three years later, in November 1700, the glass factory was leased to other Jews – brothers Nicolae and Solomon Lengyel [2, 59].

Almost a century later, in the conscription from 1785, over 8.000 Jews were registered in Transylvania. The first Jews settled in Fagaras before this year [3, 284] – apparently through two refugee families from Polish Galicia, after which others also came –, the mentioned conscription presenting a number of nine Jews in Fagaras [2, 23], probably reaching a significant number later, since they had their synagogue since the first decades of the 19th century. Moreover, the Jewish community in Fagaras was founded in 1820, and in 1827 it established the society „Chevra Kadisa (The Sacred Society - AN)” [3, 284].

It seems that dissatisfaction with the Jewish community appeared quite soon, because in 1838 the inhabitants of the city violently attacked their homes, after the expiration of a three-day ultimatum by which the Jews had been summoned to leave Fagaras. Two years later, in 1840, the Court of Vienna ordered the arrest of the instigators from Fagaras and the granting of compensation to the members of the community for the damages suffered during the unfortunate events.

After about a decade, in October 1847, the first press article with an anti-Semitic tone appeared: „The multitude of Jews nested in most of the villages of the Făgăraș district as brandy producers (spirits manufacturer – our note), is afraid that (...) will not earn one hundred percent of the brandy boiling (...).

Our poor Romanians, faithful to the evangelical commandment to love all people without distinction, pitying them, buy all the brandy from the Jews, no matter how expensive, so that they do not become poor. Who knows, maybe today or tomorrow those Israelites, getting rich, will build some Romanian churches from their own ruins, namely the United one (Greek-Catholic

– our note) in Venetia de Jos, covered in straw, the non-United one (Orthodox – our note) from Ucea, also with straw, the United one also in straw, the United church from Porumbac also covered in straw, the non-United one, covered with tiles, but made of wood and almost completely destroyed (...). Oh, Lord!” [4, 335].

A year later, on July 5, 1848, the government commissioner from Fagaras submitted a report to the government showing that protection was requested by the Jewish communities against the anti-Semites in the city [5].

In March 1852, the Ministry of Justice of the Habsburg Empire, which ruled Transylvania, issued an instruction to standardize the oath-taking procedure by Transylvanian Jews in both civil and military matters. It followed the one applied beginning with August 1846 in the other lands of the Austrian Crown, based on the codes of laws applicable to Jews starting on June 1st, 1811. Among the most important provisions, we are going to list a few:

- If a Jew was summoned by the judge for oath taking, according to the circumstances, a rabbi should also be brought as a witness, if possible;

- First, the judge had to explain to the Jew, clearly and decisively, the meaning of the object of the oath and what he has to swear upon. If he was sure that the Jew understood, the judge would remind him of what represents the violation of the oath, then read the decided formula „appropriate with the culture” and understanding of the juror;

- The judge had the obligation, before taking the oath, to inspire „into the heart of the Israelite and forcefully refresh him the sanctity of the oath, the crime and the punishment of perjury before God and the worldly judges”. If the Israelite did not make a full confession, if he spoke differently than he thought, etc., he committed perjury. It did not matter who was present, because he was swearing before God.

- By perjury, the Jew committed „a very serious crime” against the state, his fellow citizens, and against „everything that is most sacred to humanity”. According to the general laws of the country, he was also guilty of fraud, which was punishable with the shame of public exposure, with heavy imprisonment, as the case may be, and for life;

- After this exposure, the Jew was asked if he was ready to take the oath, and if he confirmed, he would put his right hand on the Torah, the second book of Moses, ch. 20, verse 7, covering his head and saying according to the president the following oath [6, 81-82]:

„I, N.N., swear by the only almighty, omnipresent and omniscient God, the holy God of Israel, who made heaven and earth, I swear with ripe meditation a pure and unfalsified oath, according to the intention and meaning of the judgment, without any hidden reserve, restraint, equivocation, without guile, deceit, or pretense, without regard to favor or promise, benefit or detriment, sympathy or antipathy, friendship or enmity, without any tendency to suppress truth or right (...)

So may Almighty God, the Lord of powers, Adonai Elohe Sabaoth, whose unspeakable name be hal-
lowed, succeed me in all my affairs, so help me in all my needs. Amen! Amen!” [7, 85].

In January 1860 was issued an order from Vienna regarding the Jews and their access to various professions: an order of the Minister of the Interior, dated „January 13 (1860), informs how His Apostolic Majesty, by the very high ordination from January 10, was too gracious to decide the termination of all those laws that exclude Jews from carrying out certain trades, in particular from the opening of pharmacies; further, in some crown lands, from wine and beer innkeeping and milling, deciding at the same time that wherever the Jews are and will settle, they can have any profession in addition to abiding the common laws. Furthermore, he endured lifting the ban, as a result of which the Jews were not allowed to live (...) also [in] Transylvania” [8, 5].

Until late, during First World War, the information about the community is no longer consistent and important. We do not yet know the total number of Jews from Fagaras who enrolled in the Austro-Hungarian army during the First World War, but we know that the number of human sacrifices among them rose to 22, dying bravely on the battlefields [3, 284].

In the fall of 1916, fearing the retaliation of the Romanian army that entered in Fagaras, because of their status as loyal subjects of the Hungarian administration, many of the Jews from Fagaras withdrew together with the officials and the functionaries beyond the Olt river and never returned [3, 284].

After December 1, 1918, the moment of the union of Transylvania with the Kingdom of Romania, several changes took place in the internal organization, according to the new realities. Thus, the Statute of the Jewish community of Fagaras is drafted, in accordance with the special laws adopted in 1929. The Statute does not explicitly state that the community is Orthodox or Neolog but instead says that it is an „autonomous community of the Congress based on the Aruchul Shulchan (Jewish Law Code – our note)” – this being, in general, the wording used by the Orthodox communities in their statutes. The statutes include all the usual regulations of community life, including membership qualifications, fees, election regulations, staff responsibilities, and many others.

In the same year, the leadership of the Jewish community in Fagaras consisted of the following members: Ignatz Löwy – rabbi; Mauriciu Thierfeld – president; Vilmos Deutsch – vice president; Oscar Mendel – cashier; Iacob Grünfeld – secretary; Izidor Halbreich – controller/verifier; Henrik Neumann – administrator; Adolf Berko and Emil Cick – administrative assistants; Adolf Tachauer – chairman of the school senate [3, 284].

After the declaration of Romania as a national-legionary state, on September 14th, 1940, Fagaras became a powerful center of activity for local legionary activists. Also, the Saxons of Fagaras organized themselves into Nazi groups and together with the Iron Guard robbed the properties of the Jews and began committing acts of violence.

From an official notification dated 21st of November 1940, we find out about the antisemitic measures in the city: „Gangs of legionaries take each Jewish store in the town by force. The owners were banished and the

shops closed, sticking posters with the inscription: «This shop will reopen on Monday, under legionary management». The remaining bandits made mock inventories, then, at gunpoint, forced the owners to sign a blank sales contract.

In this way, the shops of the following merchants were taken: 1. Samuel Cohn's widow, 2. Marcu Löbl, 3. Mendel Oscar, 4. Andor Hodoş, 5. Elena Gewölb, 6. Jacob Grünfeld, 7. Heinrich Neumann, 8. Adolf Neumann Gewölb, 9. Bernard Kaufmann, 10. Albert Licht, 11. Regina Ehrenwald, 12. Neumann Brothers, 13. Jacob Gewölb.

The Ministry of Economic Coordination of Romania ordered the restoration of the rights of the Jewish merchants, but the orders were not respected by the County Prefecture², which had a legionary leadership [9, 141].

In fact, as in almost all the cities in the country, during this month, the Jewish shops in Fagaras were „decorated on the windows and the entrance doors with posters bearing the inscriptions: «Jewish shop» or «Jewish store», or «Don't buy from the Jews» or «Attention! Jewish shop! Christians do not enter» (...)» [9, 155-156].

In the period 1940-1941, approximately half of the properties of the Jewish community in the city were confiscated: the offices, the rabbi's and officials' residences, the cultural hall, the school building, the shelter for the poor and others [10, 332].

When the deportations of the Jews to Transnistria began, they were neither allowed to take anything with them nor to practice their old occupations. Approximately 60 Jews were sent to forced labor and three of those who arrived in Transnistria died. The non-deported men, who were not mobilized for work outside the city, were employed in cleaning work or in the war industry [10, 333], at the Fagaras and Ucea de Sus factories.

During the Second World War, the Jewish properties in Fagaras were confiscated and the Jews from the neighboring villages were all held in the city. They were forced to work under extreme conditions and heavy tax obligations were imposed on them.

After the Second World War, the community was reorganized and recorded a temporary increase in the number of inhabitants, after which, through constant emigration to larger cities and the new state of Israel, the number decreased permanently [10, 333].

Demography

With the official census of 1836 were recorded 27 heads of Jewish families (owning only eight houses of their own), of which 12 were producers of spirits², 11 merchants, one tradesman, one rabbi, one teacher, and one without occupation.

Two years later, in 1838, 113 Jews were registered, in 1850 183 lived here and on the occasion of the

general census of 1857, there were three less – 180 Jews.

During the period of the Austro-Hungarian dualism (1867-1918), in all official censuses ethnic Jews – as in the case of Armenians, Gypsies, partly in the case of Ruthenians etc. –, do not appear as a distinct ethnicity, their nationality not being registered, but only their mother tongue. This situation allowed the distortion of statistical data, artificially increasing the number of ethnic Hungarians, more precisely of the „speakers” of Hungarian as their „mother tongue” [11, 540]. Consequently, the identification of the total number of Jews can only be achieved by going through the columns intended for confessional affiliation – mosaic, in our case.

According to some sources, it seems that in the middle of the 19th century, the Jewish community in Fagaras and the nearby area was the largest in southern Transylvania [10, 332].

The census of 1869 recorded a number of 276 Jews, thus, in this year, Fagaras ranked fifth in Transylvania according to the number of present Jews: Cluj – 3.008, Alba Iulia – 1.221, Târgu Mureş – 773, Dej – 351, then Bistriţa – 229, Braşov – 217, Sibiu – 168 [12, 109].

The official censuses carried out until almost our days show the following demographic parameters, from which both the progress and the regression of the Jewish population in Fagaras can be easily observed: 1880 – 262 Jews; 1890 – 485; 1900 – 474; 1910 – 514; 1920 – 457; 1930 – 388; 1947 – 360; 1956 – 181; 1966 – 93; 1977 – 54; 1992 – 11; 2003 – 3; 2022 – 0.

Since the end of the 19th century until 1914, as in the case of the Romanians, Saxons and Hungarians from Fagaras, a good part of the Jews emigrated to America, the documents of the time recording emigrants from the families Baier, Binder, Englisch, Fraisz, Gockeler, Hintz, Kesztenbaum, Löbl, Nagel, Neumann, Theil, Ziegler etc.

We are going to mention, at the end of the subtopic, only a few of the Jewish family names existing in Fagaras over time: Abraham, Ahronsohn, Apfelbaum, Ascher, Baruch, Berko, Bernat, Bock, Danzman, Finkelstein, Fischer, Fleischman, Fleissig, Freund, Fridman, Fried, Frilich, Fritsch, Fruman, Gelb, Gerl, Gittel, Gotiberger, Goldstein, Gotstein, Graufelz, Grinblat, Grinfeti, Grünfeld, Haufman, Hinsch, Hirsch, Hirschfeld, Hirschhorn, Hofman, Isak, Jakob, Josephi, Katz, Kaufman, Kestenbaum, Klein, Klerman, Kohn, Knöpfler, Kraus, Lebl, Lederer, Lewi, Licht, Litman, Lobel, Löbl, Majer, Markus, Mendel, Mojan, Mordechai, Moses, Nathan, Neuman, Rausner, Rimonof, Rosengarten, Rubin, Schabsy, Scheindel, Schnitzer, Schonberger, Schranz, Schrojer, Schwarz, Schul, Schweitzer, Silberman, Spadi, Springer, Taglicht, Thierfeld, Traub, Wachspress, Waldmeister, Weidenbaum, Weinberger, Weiss, Weisz, Wolf, Ziehn, Zimmerman, Zitter³.

² Brewing brandy was one of the basic occupations of Transylvanian Jews, during the course of history Jews were accused of „poisoning” the peasantry: „Boiling brandy and selling it is practiced in many places almost exclusively [by Jews] and they, by selling on credit, attract many of the common

folks to drink alcoholic beverages without limit, which degrades them morally, materially and physically” [2, 67].

³ It is easy to see that these are German names, the explanation being that after the middle of the 18th century, the Austrian empress Maria Theresa ordered that all Jews within the Habsburg Empire must adopt exclusively German surnames.

The Synagogue

The first synagogue in Fagaras was made out of wood around 1820 and according to other sources in 1829. In 1836 it was destroyed by a great fire and only in 1858 was it rebuilt, out of stone and brick; other authors place its building a year later, in 1859, being described as „new and modern” [10, 332]. Today, it seems to be the fifth oldest wall synagogue in Transylvania (after those in Alba Iulia – 1822-1840, Arad – 1834, Cluj Napoca – 1851, Bistrița – 1856).

On the other hand, we are informed that only following the pressure of the leadership of the city of Fagaras, the central administration of Transylvania ordered the closure of the first synagogue and its demolition within three days.

The first rabbi of the Jewish community in Fagaras was Löbl/Yehuda Silberman, active until 1864 (died on January 8), who kept for the years 1855-1863 a daily diary, which remained in manuscript, under the title „Tagebuch” or „Journal of Făgăraș”, „which is a valuable and rare memory of its kind” [3, 284], and which is kept today in the warehouses of the Central Archives for the History of the Jews in Jerusalem. In the same archives, there is also the „Registry of the Jewish Community of Făgăraș”, one of the registers of the „Hevra Kadisha” Society (1856) (others being in the archives in Budapest and Bucharest), the „Register of places in the synagogue” (1862) and a register containing the minutes of the meetings of the community management (1864). There was also an older register from 1827, which is lost and which contained a set of regulations and a list of members [10, 333].

Silberman was followed by József Cohné (Kondor), active between 1864-1874, who tried from Budapest in 1895 to reform the community [3, 284].

The next rabbi was Abraham Schull (1874-1881), although an edited source states that between the years 1875-1895 the community of Fagaras had no permanent rabbi [10, 333].

„After a longer break, between 1890-1903, the outstanding rabbi Jordán Sándor worked here”, who in the latter year moved to Satu Mare [3, 284]. He was an enthusiast Zionist, a supporter of Rónai's ideas [2, 155].

In 1904 he was succeeded by rabbi Adolf Kelemen, who died in 1916 as a military rabbi in the Austro-Hungarian army [3, 284]. He visited in 1905 the Holy Places, later publishing, in Hungarian, his travel impressions.

Alexandru Iordan followed him in the religious service for the present community - after 1918 [13, 74].

Jordan's successor was Ábrahám Isac Nebel, a supporter of Zionism⁴, but not for long (only in 1924) because he moved to the town of Salonta in Bihor county [3, 284].

During the years 1926-1929, the documents record Iona Levy as the rabbi of the community.

After the civil emancipation in 1867 and the schism at the Congress of Jews from Hungary and Transylvania (1868-1869), the community from Fagaras joined in 1869 with the Neolog organization (the

liberal, reformist current) and became Orthodox (traditionalist) in 1926.

In 1827 was established the Jewish cemetery by purchasing land, which was enlarged in 1861 [3, 284]. The cemetery was placed outside the city since its creation, in the northeastern area, where it is situated today, desolate and forgotten by all. The oldest tombstones in the cemetery date from the 19th century.

School

Around 1840, the Jewish elementary school with four classes was established, obviously of a confessional character, operating next to the Synagogue, from which the „Protocols” between the years 1864-1899 are kept at the museum in Fagaras. In this school, Jewish children acquired general knowledge in addition to ethnic studies.

Through the efforts of Rabbi J. Cohné, the school was expanded to five classes, operating with two teachers and having a modern curriculum with 50 hours per week.

After the civil emancipation of 1867, legislated by the new Austro-Hungarian dualist regime, the aforementioned Congress of the Jewish communities of Hungary and Transylvania adopted a project to organize one Mosaic confessional school in each community, secular education being left to the state elementary schools, established according to the new education law. It also envisaged the creation of centralized institutions for the training of teachers and rabbis.

The 1867 re-established school, according to the new education law, had until 1903 German as the language of instruction, after which the education process was carried out in Hungarian; from 1919, obviously, the language of instruction was Romanian.

Before 1914, Jewish schools did not have the right to issue graduation diplomas, the students were obliged to take the end-of-school-year exam in front of a committee appointed by the Ministry of Education in Budapest. Jewish students also had to pay high fees to take this exam.

In the autumn of 1916, due to the entry of the Romanian army into southern Transylvania, the school was suspended and classes were resumed only in 1919.

It was only in 1925 that a law on private education was drafted in Romania. According to the draft, private school institutions were authorized only if the founders were Romanian subjects and if they had legal personalities. Only kindergartens, primary schools, and high schools were targeted.

In the years 1924-1925, the Jewish confessional school in Fagaras was still active, but in 1929 it stopped working, „due to lack of teachers” [3, 284], and, apparently, in 1938 it was closed for good.

Among the Jews from Fagaras who graduated from secondary higher schools, we mention here two of them, who attended the courses of the Evangelical High School in Sibiu:

- Hermann Fleissig (graduated in 1873); in 1914 he was a manufacturer in Fagaras [14, 122];

- Jakob Nathanson (1878); 1914 – manufacturer in Fagaras [14, 122].

⁴ The founder of the Zionist movement in Transylvania was János Rónai, a lawyer practicing law in Fagaras.

Culture

From the available information is known the existence of several Jewish societies in Fagaras:

1. „Hevra Kadisha”, whose president was in 1929 Adolf Schönberger [3, 284];
2. The „Charity Society”, headed in 1929 by Henrik Schul [3, 284];
3. The meeting of Israelite women (with a charitable purpose), whose president was in 1929 the widow of Leopold Fleissig [3, 284];
4. „Miriam” Society, for girls;
5. A cultural association that also had a library;
6. A branch of the Transylvanian Jewish Association;
7. A band of instrumentalists;
8. Branches of various Zionist organizations [10, 333].

The economy

The Jews of Fagaras were integrated „on the fly” into the economic life of the city, obviously contributing to its development. They were primarily merchants, then craftsmen and industrialists. Other professional categories were added to them: doctors, engineers, lawyers, teachers, professors, officials, but also simple workers. The Jews also actively participated in the public life of the city, some of them periodically being members of the county and city councils [10, 332].

However, most of them dealt with trade. In a document dated September 20, 1819, issued in Brasov were recorded the debts of several people to a deceased merchant from Brasov; among them were the figure and name of a Jew from Fagaras Nathan „the Jew” [15, 652].

Before 1900, and also after, the most famous Jew was the printer and bookseller Thierfeld.

For the period 1924-1925, the Jews had the „Făgărașana” Credit Union, with a capital of 5 million lei: president Gustav Schuster, director Carol Bretz.

By professions:

- lawyers: Alfred Ludwig, Iacob Neumann, Hugo Schul;
- merchants of mixed articles: Iacob Grünfeld, Iosif Grünspan, Nathan Halbreich, Hirschorn and Co., Bernard Kaufman, Mauriciu Kästenbaum, Wilhelm Licht, the Neumann family;
- mechanical workshops: Henric Stoff;
- grocers: the Ehrenwald family, Samuel Kohn, Leopold Licht, Mendel Oscar, Maximilian Wenerich etc.;
- barbers: Emil Embacher;
- dyers: Vilma Engel;
- bakers: Carol Balthes, Adolf Englisch, Adolf Krempels, Augustin Leschner, Adolf Wazek, Ioan Zöldi (president of the Society of Bakers) etc.;
- brick and tile manufacturers: Wilhelm Krauss, Carol Krempels, Iuliu Lauritsch, Adolf Schönberger, Petru Stoff;
- innkeepers: Ignat Goldstein, V. Herscovici, Ioan Kietlsch, Emanoil Löbel, Martin Solomon;
- watchmakers: Frideric Gutlebet, Eugen Hintz and Wilhelm Rosenbaum;
- grain merchants: Friedric Hirschorn;

- shoemakers: Francisc Hampel, Francisc Hanzi, Arthur Herschornröten, Albert Molitz, Israil Schull, Johann Smidel, Ioan Welther;

- confectioners: Carol Chiba and Friederic Embacher;

- pharmacists: Carol Kontesweler;
- booksellers: the Thierfeld family;
- stone sculptors: Gabriel Herczum.

Later, a press article from 1931, with anti-Jewish content, presents all the Jewish merchant patrons, industrialists, etc. from Fagaras, the location also being indicated:

- center: „dressmaker” Hersdorffer; the only drug-store in Fagaras – Rotschild; the largest watch shop and the largest jewelry store in the city – Deutsch; clothing fabric store and the most modern tailoring – Steiner; the Thierfeld bookstore; Hotel „Weber”; bank „Schull Heinrich”; H. Schull's „big store” of colonials; „the biggest clothing and shoe store” in town – Neumann brothers; „the largest colonial and hardware store” – Thierfeld; the „big store” of clothing and shoes L. Neumann; the „big” Waro fabric store; the Fleissig alcohol factory; „Iris” perfumery; the Neumann fashion store; the Ornstein restaurant;

- Royal Street: „Turul”, shoe store; fabric store E. Gevölb; fabric shop S. Gevölb; restaurant Iszaki; Broche Gevölb fabric store; Mendel cotton shop; the „Paris” hotel and restaurant; „To the King of Socks”;

- the Jews opened their shops and taverns „at all the corners and exits of the city”: Sicht, Havasi, Genardt, Neumann, Somberger, Kaufmann, Halbreich et al.;

- also, gasoline in the city and county of Fagaras was supplied by the Jew Hirschorn [16, 138].

Notable people

József Cohné. He was born in 1834 in the town of Szentpéter, Zala county (located in the south-west of Hungary). His important works were: „Philosophia geneeseo” (edited in Prague, in 1862), „Az emberi jog vagy a jedú és a pénez” (Sibiu, 1868), „Egység és elválás” (Fagaras, 1869), „A hármás alap” (Budapest, 1874) and „Juden der Revolution” (Arad, 1880).

For Fagaras is also mentioned the name of Aron Dornzweig, who came from Lemberg and was involved in the education of children. Although he died at only 26 years old, he managed to publish three volumes of poems in Hebrew, being situated from this point of view among the first in Transylvania. The first volume, „Nevel Vekino” („Harp and Violin”), appeared in Sibiu in 1873 and is considered to be the first Hebrew creation with a Jewish author to appear in Transylvania [2, 122].

In 1929, among the important people of the Jews here were also recorded: Aron Speiser – major (deceased); Hochman Nándor – military doctor (deceased); Henrik Lessmann – chief physician of the former Fagaras county; Adolf Tachauer – chief veterinarian of the former county of Fagaras; Martón Haber – chief engineer at the railway [3, 284].

Conclusions

Although the first contacts of the Jews with Fagaras date back to the middle of the 16th century, their

settlement in the city on the left bank of the Olt River dates back only to the end of the 18th century.

Their number grew relatively quickly, it immediately reached, in the 1820s, the establishment of the Jewish community with its own statutes and the establishment of the necessary institutions for any community – the Synagogue and the School.

As anywhere in the world, the Jews settled in Fagaras devoted themselves to the greatest extent to economic activities, which they practiced continuously until the beginning of the Second World War, when the historical-political realities led to persecution and even to their murder, in many cases.

Although their demographic decline in Fagaras began after 1918-1919, most of them began to leave, en masse, to larger cities or to settle in the new state of Israel only from the early years of the communist regime in Romania, therefore today there is not a single Jew in the city, only the Synagogue carrying on the memory of their presence in these lands.

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